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PSYCHOLOGICAL COMPONENTS OF TEACHER'S CULTURE IN LANGUAGE, SPEECH AND COMMUNICATION

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Abstract: The thesis deals with the concept of teacher's cultural competence and reflects the structural model of psychological culture of class teacher by providing key communication skills for educators.

Key words: psychological literacy, psychological health, emotional culture, non-verbal communication, empathy.

XXI century is the age of global reforms and scientific turns. The current stage of modernization of education put forward higher requirements for the training of teachers. This should be a creative minded person, communicative leader who can effectively influence the audience. Therefore, a prerequisite professionalism of the teacher is the high culture of his speech and communication.

The work of the teacher is aimed at shaping the personality of a growing person, it contributes to the development of certain rules of behavior, provides intellectual development of a person. In order to be able to interact correctly with other people, and especially with learners, the teacher must possess not only special knowledge in the subject, but also professional communication skills. We can confidently say that the teacher's speech is the main tool of pedagogical influence and at the same time a model for students.

For professionally competent, successful and effective realization of their duties, teachers ought to be familiar with the psychological and pedagogical basics of working with learners of specific age, be informed about the latest advancements in forms and methods of educational work, know and use modern educational technologies.

The central element of the teacher's professionalism is his or her professional psychological-pedagogical competence, the understanding of the complexity of personality, ability to analyze interaction of learners with the world, and manifestations of the learner's interpersonal relations with other people. Thus, the psychological culture can be viewed as a part of psychological and pedagogical competence of a teacher.

Psychological understanding of culture defines people as both cultural objects and subjects, and this demands that to the definition of culture should be

added with a set of values, norms and ideals, actively internalized by people and used by them in interactions with others.

Consideration of the psychological culture phenomenon within an educational context is attributed to the fact that the pedagogical reality needs to introduce the emotional component to the educational process and actualize personal resources of its participants. Psychological culture is a socio-psychological mechanism of effective adaptation within the society; it facilitates social and cultural interaction and plays an important role in maintaining psychological health and quality of all activities, including the educational one.

True psychological culture of teachers is the culture of their beliefs, experiences, ideas and influences, manifested in their attitude towards themselves and their students. Applying the components of psychological culture on personality of a teacher, it is necessary to emphasize the interconnection of the three main components: culture of pedagogical reflection, emotional culture, and culture of pedagogical influence.

Psychological literacy, being the minimum requirement of the psychological culture, assumes integrity of personality and a certain mind-set. Psychological literacy may manifest itself in broad general knowledge about various psychological phenomena, gained by both scientific and everyday experience, derived from traditions, customs, direct contacts with other people, learned from the mass media, and so on.

Psychological health is the result of normal development of the subjective reality within an individual. It characterizes the person as a whole, shapes the manifestations of one's spirit and serves as a diagnostic indicator of possible problems in the psychological domain of a person. The modern interpretation of psychological health states positive attitude towards themselves, the optimal mental development, personal growth and self-actualization, mental integration, balance, personal autonomy, appropriate social behavior, the ability to understand self and others, the ability to make choices and take responsibility for it.

The personality-oriented education, in terms of which we view the **self-reflective component** of teacher's activities, focuses on the development of personal-semantic sphere of a teacher – an ability to reflect on the reality and its value. Reflection is meditation on the goals, process and the results of one's internalization of culture, as well as awareness of the inner changes in one's personality. Reflection is both the main cognitive mean of self-awareness and self-regulation, and a mechanism of self-development. A teacher should know

the culture of self-acceptance and be able to express him- or herself in many different and sometimes unexpected qualities, feelings, actions. The high level of self-acceptance determines not only stable Self-concept, but also such of other people.

The other important component of teachers' psychological culture is their **emotional culture**. It is necessary for every teacher and its development begins with attempts to analyze one's emotional experience, to listen oneself carefully, separating true unconditional emotions from destructive judgments. The emotional culture of a teacher is an indicator of his or her general psychological culture. Education has high expectations for emotional sphere of teachers. The most prominent signs of teacher's emotional culture are high level of emotional resilience, empathy and emotional flexibility. Emotional culture reflects the level of professionalism, emotional maturity and influences reputation of a teacher.

Therefore, the **emotional culture** of a teacher is:

- an ability to understand and know oneself (strengths and weaknesses, feelings and behaviors);
- an ability to regulate oneself (attitudes, behavior, decision-making, persistence, flexibility, coping with stress and resolution of conflicts, control over emotions);
- an ability to motivate oneself (set goals and plan actions, achieving goals, positive attitude, joy of life and satisfaction from work);
- an ability to understand others, their emotions, feelings, reasons, behavior, be patient;
- an ability to build relationships with the others (trust, respect, flexibility, teamwork).

Psychological culture of teacher includes one more important component – the **culture of teacher's influence**. Culture of pedagogical influence implies replacing authoritarian direct influence on children with the developmental one. In this case the main and primary concern of a teacher is creating positive environment for unhindered intellectual, moral, aesthetic, and any other development of learners, i.e., the development in accordance with learners' own goals, intentions and aspirations.

Communication skills can be defined as the transmission of a message that involves the shared understanding between the contexts in which the communication takes place. In addition, teacher communication skills are important for a teacher in delivery of education to students . Effective communication skills are really important for a teacher in transmitting of

education, classroom management and interaction with students in the class. Teacher has to teach the students having different thinking approaches. To teach in accordance with the ability and capability of the students a teacher need to adopt such skills of communication which motivate the students toward their learning process .

A variety of skills are needed for good teaching and teachers.

Non- verbal communication

- Body language
- Tone of voice
- Gestures
- Facial expressions

Empathy

- Showing respect for learners' point of view, even when you do not agree
- Having a sense goodwill or kindness
- Valuing the experience, knowledge and commitment learners bring to a partnership
- Being aware of the difficulties and challenges learners face

Active listening

- Attending
- Following
- Pauses and silences
- Reflecting
- Prioritizing

The following categories of teacher's speech culture are essential:

- correctness,
- accuracy,
- logicalness,
- expressiveness,
- richness,
- purity,
- appropriateness.

The following units are not characteristic to purity of teacher's speech culture:

- 1) dialectal words, phrases, grammatical forms, stress and pronunciation;
- 2) inappropriate usage of foreign words and phrases (barbarism);
- 3) slang and jargon words and phrases;
- 4) insulting and offensive words and phrases (vulgarisms);

5) parasite words;

6) bureaucratic language (very official words that are difficult to understand).

In conclusion, the choice of an educational strategy or of kind of influence is always left to a teacher. Teachers simply need to remember that “it takes a personality to form a personality, and it takes character to form character”.

A teacher must be a Person, as it is his or her professional characteristics. Therefore, the development of future teachers' psychological culture that would serve as a mechanism for effective communication, understanding, and communication between people of different nationalities, age, gender, occupation and other characteristics, is the basis of the psychological safety of both modern learners and the educational environment in general.

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